

On infinite nested series and the Riemann hypothesis

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Abstract

The relation between nested infinite series and the Riemann zeta function is examined and it is used to derive limits for infinite sums as well as to assert that all the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function lie on the critical line. These results may have profound implications beyond number theory, affecting other areas of mathematics as well as quantum physics, cryptography, and computer science.

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1 Introduction

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s}$, which was first introduced by Leonard Euler [1], was extended to the complex plane by Bernhard Riemann, who also exposed its connection to the distribution of prime numbers through the Riemann hypothesis [2]. The Riemann Hypothesis asserts that the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function (those that are not negative even integers) lie on the critical line where the real part of s satisfies $\Re(s) = 1/2$ in the complex plane. A proof of the Riemann Hypothesis has been elusive ever since it was proposed by Bernhard Riemann in 1859.

2 Nested infinite sums

Let us first examine the expansion of the square of $\zeta(s)$ in the region $\Re(s) > 1$ where $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s}$ is known to converge:

$$\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} \right)^2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-2s} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} \sum_{m=n+1}^{\infty} m^{-s}. \quad (1)$$

Substituting $\sum_{m=n+1}^{\infty} m^{-s} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} m^{-s} - \sum_{m=1}^n m^{-s}$ in equation 1 results in:

$$\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} \right)^2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-2s} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} m^{-s} - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} \sum_{m=1}^n m^{-s}, \quad (2)$$

which allows to express the nested infinite sum on the right-hand side as a function of ζ :

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n n^{-s} m^{-s} = \frac{1}{2} [\zeta(2s) + \zeta(s)^2]. \quad (3)$$

The series in 3 can be generalized by allowing different exponents, and by further nesting. Nevertheless these are not needed for the purpose of this manuscript.

From the relation to the Riemann ζ function derived in equation 3 the following properties for $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n n^{-s} m^{-s}$ are observed:

1. The series converges for $s > 1$.
2. The analytic continuation of the series to the complex plane is given by $\frac{1}{2} [\zeta(2s) + \zeta(s)^2]$, where s is a complex number.
3. The series with its analytic continuation has two poles, $s = 1/2$ and $s = 1$.
4. The series shares the trivial zeros of the Riemann ζ function located at $-2k$ where k is a positive integer.

3 Evaluating infinite sums

Equation 3 allows to evaluate infinite convergent sums, as well as Ramanujan sums [3] for divergent infinite series who are instead assigned the value of their analytical continuation. Examples for $s = 2, 4$ and Ramanujan sums (marked with $\Re$) for $s = -1, -3$ are:

$$1 + \frac{1}{2^2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2^2} \right] + \frac{1}{3^2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} \right] + \frac{1}{4^2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} \right] + \dots = \frac{7}{360} \pi^4,$$

$$1 + \frac{1}{2^4} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2^4} \right] + \frac{1}{3^4} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2^4} + \frac{1}{3^4} \right] + \frac{1}{4^4} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2^4} + \frac{1}{3^4} + \frac{1}{4^4} \right] + \dots = \frac{13}{113400} \pi^8,$$

$$1 + 2[1 + 2] + 3[1 + 2 + 3] + 4[1 + 2 + 3 + 4] + \dots = \frac{1}{288} \quad (\Re),$$

$$1 + 2^3[1 + 2^3] + 3^3[1 + 2^3 + 3^3] + 4^3[1 + 2^3 + 3^3 + 4^3] + \dots = \frac{1}{28800} \quad (\Re).$$

4 The Riemann Hypothesis

The non-trivial zeros s_0 of the Riemann zeta function can be inspected using equation 3 and the condition:

$$\zeta(s_0) = 0. \quad (4)$$

Equation 4 determines the trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function. The result of evaluating the expression 4 in equation 3 allows to look for the zeros s_0 by solving the equation:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n n^{-s_0} m^{-s_0} = \frac{1}{2} \zeta(2s_0). \quad (5)$$

In order to be able to apply the theory of Dirichlet series to equation 5 let us employ the auxiliary Dirichlet series:

$$D_a(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n n^{-s} m^{-s_0} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n^s}, \quad \text{where } a_n = \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{1}{m^{s_0}}$$

$$D_b(s) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} n^{-s_0} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n^s}, \quad \text{where } b_n = \frac{1}{2n^{s_0}} \quad (6)$$

The question of what the solutions to equation 5 are, can be then reasked as the more general question: are there any $s = s_0$ for which the Dirichlet series $D_a(s)$ and $D_b(s)$ are equal, as defined in the expressions 6?

In order to address this question, the regions of absolute convergence for the series given in the expressions 6 have to be established. Let us refer to the real parts $\Re(s)$, $\Re(s_0)$ as σ , σ_0 respectively. The definition $D_b(s) = \frac{1}{2} \zeta(s + s_0)$, implies that the series $D_b(s)$ converges absolutely for $\sigma > 1 - \sigma_0$. On the other hand, the absolute convergence of $D_a(s)$ requires the convergence of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{a_n}{n^s} \right|$. Given that:

$$|a_n| = \left| \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{1}{m^{s_0}} \right| \leq \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{1}{|m^{s_0}|} = \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{1}{m^{\sigma_0}} < n, \quad \forall \sigma_0 > 0, \quad (7)$$

the following inequality also holds:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{a_n}{n^s} \right| < \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{n}{n^{\sigma}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{\sigma-1}} \quad (8)$$

The inequality 8 implies that the series $D_a(s)$ converges absolutely for $\sigma > 2$, as long as $\sigma_0 > 0$. The latter is ensured by the known fact that the real part σ_0 of the zeros of the ζ function lie within the critical strip $0 < \sigma_0 < 1$.

Because $\sigma_0 > 0$, and the Dirichlet series $D_a(s)$ and $D_b(s)$ converge absolutely for $\sigma > 1 - \sigma_0$ and $\sigma > 2$ respectively, it follows that both series share the common region of absolute convergence $\sigma > 2$.

The coefficients of the Dirichlet series $D_a(s)$ and $D_b(s)$ satisfy $a_n \neq b_n, \forall n$, which implies that the series are different in their common region of absolute convergence $\sigma > 2$. Following the uniqueness theorem for Dirichlet series, this implies that the series and their analytical continuation have to be different for all s , except perhaps for trivial isolated points, zeros or poles. Since s_0 is neither a zero nor a pole of $\zeta(2s)$ it follows that the equation 5 has no solution:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^n n^{-s_0} m^{-s_0} \neq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-2s_0}, \quad \forall s_0 \mid \Re(2s_0) \neq 1. \quad (9)$$

The inequality 9 does not apply for $\Re(2s_0) = 1$ because there is a common pole at $2s_0 = 1$.

Therefore the only blind spot in the inequality 9, where the expressions are undefined and hence where the zeros can lie, is at the common abscissa of convergence $\Re(s_0) = 1/2$ defined by the common pole. In other words, the zeros could only hide precisely at the boundary between the region where the series on the right-hand side converges (to the right of the abscissa) and the region where the series needs to be analytically continued (to the left of the abscissa). Since the two sides of the equation 9 share the common pole $s_0 = 1/2$, the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function can only be hidden in the line $\sigma_0 = \Re(s_0) = 1/2$.

Two points to notice are:

- This result tells that in the case that non-trivial zeros s_0 of the Riemann zeta function exist, they have to obey $\Re(s_0) = 1/2$.
- The equation 5 is to the non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function what equation 4 is to its trivial zeros.

References

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